

Kathak Dance and Neuroplasticity: Implications for Cognitive Health

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Abstract

Dance is a complex form of physical and emotional expression; in addition to providing embodiment and communication, it also offers many neurological benefits and is a creative art form. This article focuses on Kathak, an Indian classical dance that involves rhythm, coordination, and emotional cognition, along with other neurologically beneficial factors. By engaging many parts of the brain, such as the hippocampus and cerebellum, dance strengthens synapses and other functional neural pathways, which boosts brain health. The review also explores how neuroplasticity can affect learning and memory, and it especially highlights key frameworks, such as increased levels of brain-derived neurotropic factors and synaptogenesis. Emphasis is also placed on elderly populations and individuals who may have neurodegenerative conditions such as Alzheimer's and Parkinson's disease, where dance has many positive effects. Although it can't completely prevent neurodegenerative diseases, it can certainly delay or slow progression and provide calming benefits for individuals suffering from these diseases. Overall, this article reviews how dance is an approachable form of art that has many cognitive benefits; it supports neuroplasticity, cognitive resilience, and strong neurological health throughout life.

Keywords: Kathak, Neuroplasticity, Brain Derived Neurotropic Factor (BDNF), Parkinson's Disease, Alzheimer's Disease, Neurodegenerative Diseases, Neural pathways, Functional plasticity, Oxidative stress

1. Neural Factors Behind Dance

Dance is a complex and multifaceted form of art. It involves rhythm and movement, serving a deeper purpose of conveying feelings and telling a story. However, dance offers benefits that extend beyond communication; it provides numerous neurological and psychological advantages, and can help shape the brain into its healthiest version. Firstly, research demonstrates that dance can activate multiple regions of the brain, particularly the brain's reward centers and sensory circuits, offering benefits such as improved focus and coordination [1]. Additionally, Indian dance can specifically provide benefits in coordination, memory, and even enhance neuroplasticity. Neuroplasticity, which refers to the brain's ability to change, grow, and adapt, was first introduced by William James in 1890, yet the term was actually coined by the neuroscientist Jerzy Konorski. William James presented his ideas in a book titled "The Principles of Psychology", the first person to actually consider the idea that the brain can adapt, change, and reorganize itself. Later on, Konorski suggested that a neuron that has been fired can contribute to the plasticity made in the brain. Although both of these scientists brought attention to the concept of neuroplasticity, later research has expanded on their theory and even demonstrated how the brain can change in response to learning, experience, and environment.

In fact, neuroplasticity can affect the neurons of the brain and even multiple different parts of the brain [2]. Neuroplasticity can aid in learning new skills, but it can also help mitigate the effects of brain injuries and neurological diseases, such as Alzheimer's.

Neuroplasticity can help delay or even prevent neurological diseases; it can also help change the way people think and feel [3]. Even though neurogenesis is the production of neural cells that starts at 3 weeks old in the womb and is known to have stopped when babies are born, new research shows how this process occurs throughout one's whole life, which shows that neuroplasticity is something that can occur during any stage in life. Overall, neuroplasticity helps the brain adapt. This allows change to occur throughout life and demonstrates the importance of neuroplasticity for various aspects, including learning new skills and even altering one's self-perception. Neuroplasticity is specifically very important for the brain, as it's the brain's ability to form and recognize neural connections. Neuroplasticity offers numerous benefits, including enhanced learning, improved cognitive functions, and skill development. Most importantly, it keeps the brain healthy.

Indian classical dance is known for its expressive gestures and movements. Kathak, specifically, is a renowned dance form originating from North India that uses rhythmic footwork, harmonized music, and graceful footwork [4]. Kathak also offers multiple cognitive benefits, including enhanced memory and attention, as well as improved cognitive functions [5]. Kathak dancers employ intricate footwork and storytelling, which stimulate different parts of the brain and improve cognitive functions such as spatial reasoning and memory. Additionally, Kathak dancers express their emotions and feelings through dance, which helps reduce stress. Since stress is linked to harmful effects on the brain, dance helps alleviate these effects and reduces pressure, thereby

increasing relaxation [6]. Focusing more on the memory aspect, as Kathak dancers learn new tala and tukras, the process of remembering all the steps and learning them efficiently requires working memory. Over time, as dancers continue to practice and learn, this memory becomes increasingly stable, and eventually they develop strong memory thresholds [7]. Dance also helps alleviate anxiety, as it can be a calming experience at times. This helps reduce both structural and functional changes in the brain [8]. Additionally, the coordination between the hands and feet in Kathak is linked to cognitive flexibility, which keeps the mind active and strong. Especially for neuroplasticity, elderly individuals who practice any type of dance regularly usually develop stronger brain plasticity, which helps strengthen the brain, create new memory links and connections, and allows the brain to adapt and change more easily. The improvement in neuroplasticity enhances not only cognitive abilities but also motor functions, resulting in overall better health[9]. Overall, dance may be a beautiful art form, yet it is also an impeccable tactic for brain health and even for reducing the risk of neurodegenerative diseases in the future. Dance is a fun way for people of any age to relax and get a physical workout while improving their overall health. Kathak, especially, is a great way to reduce stress and improve cognitive abilities simultaneously.

Brain-derived neurotrophic factor (BDNF) plays a crucial role in the growth, development, and maintenance of neurons, as well as the formation and strengthening of neural connections, and even promotes neuroplasticity. Usually, if the brain is derived from the BDNF, it can be linked with negative effects, such as neurodegenerative

diseases, including Alzheimer's, Parkinson's disease, and multiple sclerosis[10]. This factor specifically plays a role in learning and memory; changes associated with this factor are usually due to aging or psychiatric disease[11]. BDNF, in particular, is found in the central nervous system, where it helps synapses and neurons grow and remain healthy, which is crucial for the brain to communicate effectively. Usually, BDNF is more abundant in hippocampal cells and the hippocampus, which is responsible for memory, learning, and other cognitive functions [12]. Furthermore, dance can actually help increase the levels of BDNF in the brain. Due to this, dance can help maintain a healthy brain as it ages and improve cognitive functions [13]. BDNF also plays a role in neuroplasticity and the prevention of neurodegenerative diseases. Studies show that when elderly patients dance, their memory and coordination begin to improve due to higher levels of BDNF in the blood. With occasional practice, it can help the elderly who may already suffer some cognitive decline; even though it may not completely stop neurodegenerative diseases from occurring, it can definitely push the process to occur later on[14]. In conclusion, BDNF plays a crucial role in maintaining the health of brain neurons, leading to improvements in cognitive functions and overall brain health. Dancing, especially, is a good way to increase levels of this factor in the brain and have fun while doing so!

2. How dance activates brain regions

While dance is being performed, multiple different regions of the brain are being activated. In fact, the somatosensory cortex, motor cortex, and cerebellum are all utilized in learning dance and performing. The motor cortex is mostly used for planning,

while the somatosensory cortex is used for motor control and coordination (both very important for certain dances like kathak). The cerebellum is also used for more advanced motor-related movement[15]. Dance also engages numerous brain networks, including those involved in perception. The rhythm used in dance is also processed cyclically in specific brain regions[16]. This activation of multiple brain regions keeps it sharp and strong. Most importantly, while the motor cortex is being used during dancing, it serves a very strong purpose, as it sends signals down the spine to the different parts of the body to perform that specific movement[17]. In addition to these different motor parts of the brain, dance also activates the prefrontal cortex, which is crucial for focus and memory recall, playing a significant role in learning choreography. The hippocampus also forms memories and starts to recognize spatial patterns while dance is being performed. Finally, the limbic system and orbitofrontal cortex can also be activated, which are especially important for motivation and emotion. Since these regions are also activated, it demonstrates how dance is particularly linked to joy and other emotional release feelings that follow. Together, the activation of all these different areas of the brain improves physical and mental health, as well as enhances other important factors, such as neuroplasticity.

3. Neuroplasticity: Functional and Structural Changes

Neuroplasticity (the ability of the brain to adapt and change) causes many different structural and functional changes to the brain. Essentially, it involves how the nervous system can alter its activity by reorganizing the brain's structure and connections. It's literally how the brain can change after an injury or other trauma, such as a brain

tumor[18]. In fact, there are two main types of neuroplasticity: functional plasticity and structural plasticity. Functional plasticity is the process by which the brain can move functions from injured sections of the brain to sections that aren't injured or affected. Structural plasticity refers to the brain's ability to change its structure after learning new things [19]. To go more in depth, structural plasticity involves not only the physical changes in the brain, but it also impacts synaptogenesis, which is the making of new synapses. Typically, as synaptogenesis is being remodeled in the brain, other structural changes also occur. Structural plasticity is also crucial after injuries, as synapse formation and dendritic sprouting occur, which is essential for the brain to relearn skills after a major tumor or stroke[20]. In contrast, functional plasticity actually changes damaged parts of the brain to the undamaged parts. This process is usually faster at the beginning and then gradually slows down as it continues. Usually, neural paths that perform other functions take over the function that was damaged[21]. In conclusion, both types of plasticity are closely connected, as one facilitates the formation of new neural pathways and the other reinforces them. Over time, these become stronger through long-term potential, and pathways that are not used frequently start to weaken. Ultimately, neuroplasticity is very important for the brain to remain adaptable throughout life. It helps with many things, such as adapting to new environments, recovering from injuries, or learning new skills. It is crucial for learning throughout life and recovery.

4. Performances: Neuroplastic Benefits

Performances enhance neuroplasticity in many different ways. Usually, every type of sport involves exercise, which enhances motor skills. Over time, as these motor movements are repeatedly used, neuroplasticity becomes stronger[22]. Similarly, dance requires higher skills such as coordination and rhythm, which are important for physical and cognitive benefits. As dancers continue to practice and perform, these neural pathways strengthen, and so do the synaptic connections that are crucial for motor coordination and balance. Different types of performances also influence the degree of neuroplasticity enhancement. Typically, dance performances with more music and rhythm alter neural networks and enhance cognitive functions[23]. Certain performances that require more practice also increase the gray and white matter in the brain in different regions, which is important for controlling bodily functions[24]. Dance specifically is very important for reducing the risk of neurodegenerative diseases and increasing neuroplasticity. Especially performing in front of an audience adds emotion, which ultimately releases neurotransmitters, specifically dopamine, a key factor in motivation and learning. Overall, dance is important for strengthening the body and enhancing the brain's adaptability and resilience through neuroplasticity.

5. Neurodegenerative Diseases and Brain Function

Many different types of neurodegenerative diseases exist. Neurodegenerative diseases are primarily chronic conditions characterized by the progressive loss of neurons in the brain and nervous system. It affects various aspects, including mobility, coordination, and memory. Some of the main types of neurodegenerative diseases include Alzheimer's, Parkinson's disease, dementia, atrophic lateral sclerosis (ALS), and

multiple sclerosis. To go deeper, Alzheimer's is a disease that affects memory and thinking, and it's a disease that progressively keeps getting worse. It mostly affects the synapses in neurons, which in turn affects their ability to function properly. Parkinson's disease is a disease that mostly has an impact on movement and results in less coordination and balance, and also gets worse over time[25]. Dementia is a neurodegenerative disease similar to Alzheimer's, but they are not the same; dementia has many contributing factors and is more of a group of symptoms. Some symptoms of dementia include difficulties with problem-solving, memory loss, loss of control over movements, and even emotional challenges such as anxiety or depression[26]. ALS is also a progressive disease that gets worse over time as it damages nerve cells in areas of the brain and spinal cord, which causes muscle weakness and eventually, paralysis. Mostly, motor neurons are affected in this disease, and over time, basic functions such as eating and breathing also become increasingly difficult. Neurodegenerative diseases are a broad category of diseases that progressively damage the nervous system. If someone is affected by this disease, parts of the brain start to die due to the degradation of brain cells, which makes daily life, then eventually survival, nearly impossible. These diseases are not that common, but still have a strong chance of affecting anyone over the age of 65. The symptoms associated with neurodegenerative diseases can also actually vary in people, as every brain is different, and the disease occurs in people due to different reasons, causing variation. If one is diagnosed with this disease, the damage is often indefinite, and the quality of life can be forever affected. Many of the medications that do exist also don't stop the spread of this horrible disease, and due to the heavy

amount of pathogenic factors involved with neurodegenerative diseases, the chance of surviving long-term remains slim[27]. Even though neurodegenerative diseases are caused mainly by the dysfunction of proteins, many other factors, like oxidative stress and environmental factors, can also affect disease development. Despite the amount of research that people put into this disease, the pathogen that causes it still remains unclear, making it one of the most complex diseases to ever exist[28]. Finally, this disease is something that affects over 35 million people around the world. Many types of these neurodegenerative conditions give people only a few years to live. Ongoing research is being conducted by neuroscientists every day, and many of their new studies are exploring techniques such as gene therapy, which involves altering genes in a person, and targeted medication, which is specifically designed to target amyloid plaques/ other brain regions responsible for neurodegenerative diseases. Neuroplasticity and life factors are also being studied by neuroscientists to see what type of change they can have on these neurodegenerative conditions. Cognitive impairments are problems associated with different cognitive abilities such as thinking, learning, memory, and coordination[29], [30]. These cognitive impairments affect most of our mental processes, which ultimately make everyday life complicated. Typically, individuals with mild cognitive impairments can still function independently throughout the day, though they may notice some changes. In contrast, those with major cognitive impairments experience more severe changes and require daily assistance [31]. Cognitive impairments can particularly affect individuals over the age of 65 and have a significant impact on memory, speech, and other vital functions. Some types of cognitive

impairments include frontotemporal dementia (loss of nerve cells related to personality changes), vascular dementia (brain damage due to insufficient blood flow), Alzheimer's disease (characterized by memory loss), and Lewy body dementia (affects nerve cells and causes motor symptoms)[32]. Overall, cognitive impairments affect normal functions in everyday life that are very important for survival. In advanced stages of this disease, medical support becomes mandatory.

6. Dance with Parkinson's Disease Management

Dance is beneficial for various reasons, one of which includes reducing the risk of neurodegenerative diseases. Parkinson's, a neurodegenerative disease, is a progressive disease that affects movement and kills brain cells. For this disease, the most common treatments include medication and other medical treatments. Other factors, such as singing and dancing, are also very important as they allow patients with this disease to express themselves, which is something that can be particularly challenging for people suffering from this disease to achieve. Most importantly, dance can combine elements of these other treatments, which ultimately help manage some Parkinson's symptoms and improve quality of life [33]. Research has also shown that individuals with speech and movement problems who participate in dance classes experience improvements in their psychological well-being and benefit from a therapeutic effect, which is particularly important for managing Parkinson's disease [34]. Dance also includes all factors that can be changed by Parkinson's disease, such as coordination and strength. This is

crucial for maintaining optimal health while living with this disease [35]. Since the current medications for Parkinson's aren't strong enough and don't have a very strong effect, dance serves as a therapeutic alternative medication for people with this disease[36]. Dance also releases dopamine, a stress-relieving hormone that improves mood and enhances movement. Dance helps patients with this disease stay motivated while simultaneously improving their cognitive abilities and brain health. Even though dance can't completely treat Parkinson's, it can play a big role in delaying the disease and improving some functions that degrade with this disease. In addition, the combination of music and rhythm is way more effective than taking drugs that aren't as impactful. Dance not only helps patients living with and suffering from Parkinson's disease, but it also helps improve their quality of life to the best extent possible. Especially dancing in groups can help with social interaction, which in turn helps alleviate emotional symptoms. In conclusion, dance offers a range of benefits and can serve as a valuable tool in supporting individuals with various neurodegenerative diseases.

7. Conclusions

Dance is far more than a form of artistic expression; it is a powerful tool for promoting brain health and enhancing neuroplasticity. Through the activation of multiple brain regions, including the motor cortex, cerebellum, hippocampus, and limbic system, dance strengthens cognitive, motor, and emotional functions. Indian classical dance forms such as Kathak, which emphasize rhythm, coordination, storytelling, and emotional

expression, uniquely engage working memory, attention, and cognitive flexibility, making them especially effective in supporting neural adaptation. Neuroplasticity plays a critical role in learning, recovery from injury, and resilience against neurological decline. As demonstrated throughout this article, dance promotes both structural and functional plasticity by reinforcing neural pathways, encouraging synaptogenesis, and increasing levels of BDNF, which is essential for neuronal survival and memory formation. These changes are particularly significant for aging populations and individuals at risk for or living with neurodegenerative diseases. In conditions such as Parkinson's disease, where current medical treatments often fail to fully address motor and cognitive symptoms, dance emerges as a valuable complementary therapy. By combining physical movement, music, rhythm, and emotional engagement, dance enhances motivation, coordination, mood, and overall quality of life. While dance cannot cure neurodegenerative diseases, it has the potential to delay disease progression, alleviate symptoms, and preserve functional independence.

Ultimately, dance represents an accessible, enjoyable, and scientifically supported approach to strengthening the brain across all stages of life. By fostering neuroplasticity and cognitive resilience, dance not only enriches artistic expression but also serves as a meaningful strategy for maintaining neurological health and reducing the impact of neurodegenerative diseases in the future.

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